

An effective approach for the improvement in efficacy of life saving filter typed safety breathing apparatus

A. Kumar^{a*}, Bijent Kr. Poddar^b, S. K. Sinha^c and L. Kumari^c

^aBio-Environment Division, CIMFR, Barwa Road, Dhanbad-826 015, Jharkhand, India

^bIIT-FITJEE Centre, Dhanbad-824 004, Jharkhand, India

^cP. K. Roy Memorial College, Dhanbad-826 004, Jharkhand, India

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Abstract : Filter typed self rescuer (FSR) is a traditional safety breathing apparatus to make breathable air free from carbon monoxide and dust. The performance evaluation of canister of FSR from different manufacturing companies such as Joseph Leslie Dragger (Germany), Hunan Coal Company (China), Fraser (Poland) and MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata were evaluated as per IS 9563 : 1980 by open circuit artificial mechanical human lung simulation machine. According to Indian standard the breathing resistance and conversion of carbon monoxide into non-poisonous carbon dioxide gas was found rational in the FSR of MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata. The scope for modification exists in the canister of FSR for reducing the inhalation temperature and dust filter to improve its duration of action.

Keywords : Filter typed self rescuer, catalyst, hopcalite, breathing-resistance, dust arrester, improvement, fire and explosion.

Introduction

Disasters are normally of two types such as natural disaster and manmade disaster. Nature based disaster are tsunami, earthquake or high speed cyclone whereas manmade disaster are Bhopal gas tragedy, Sago coalmines explosion in USA, Nagda coalmine explosion in Jharkhand and Mahabir Colliery in West Bengal, fire in high rise building like Eliphinston enclave at Kolkata etc. In all the adverse situation of disaster, life saving is very important for human. Safety breathing apparatus may not be effective during nature based disaster but it can save life during manmade disaster.

Human resources which are employed for the operation of industrial activities and the huge manpower are in direct touch with the industrial processes. In this nationality the workers are at risk of arising out any industrial accident or misfortune of disaster. The concern industries are of various category such as mining, chemical, thermal power, cement, oil refineries, etc. The industrial process are so complex and inter connected with each other that it cannot be risk free. Despite all efforts of preventive safety measures, accident may occur and cause huge loss to human life, value of social property, envi-

ronment and legal aspect related to compensation. Safety during the industrial production has become an important and an inevitable issue parallel to the main stream of production. At some stage disaster due to underground mine fire and explosion, breathing becomes difficult for survival of human being and crisis of breathable air constantly exists. Safety norms are specified to fight with the poisonous carbon monoxide gas present in the underground mine environment and carrying of safety breathing apparatus is mandatory.

Effect of carbon monoxide gas in human respiration :

Carbon monoxide gas reduces cellular respiration of neurons of brain and make it inactive due lack of oxygen called hypoxia. Carbon monoxide combined with haemoglobin of the blood and form CO-Hb (carboxy-haemoglobin). The ability of CO gas to combine with haemoglobin is 250 time more faster than that of oxygen to form oxy haemoglobin in human blood¹. Due to this, 1/250 of the normal partial pressure of 100 mm Hg for oxygen is required to combine with haemoglobin while only at 0.4 mm Hg partial pressure at 0.1% of CO combines with almost half of the blood of the human body. It noticeably reduces the oxygen carrying capacity of the blood and

causes cardiac-respiratory failure. The person when come out in fresh air from CO exposure and breaths in normal air, the CO-Hb shows reversible phenomena and its break in to

The half life ($t_{1/2}$) of CO-Hb is 5 to 6 h. The person when exposed to 100% pure oxygen it reduces to 1.5 h. In critical cases the hyperbaric oxygen therapy at 2 to 3 atmospheric pressure the half life of breaking of CO-Hb reduces to 25 min². In few literatures, the victim of CO exposure can also be benefitted by simultaneously administered 5% of CO₂ with pure oxygen. The addition of CO₂ increases the alveolar ventilation and release of CO from haemoglobin of blood become faster³.

The percentage of CO in atmosphere and the corresponding to formation of CO-Hb with its physiological effect are summarised as below⁴.

CO (%) in atmosphere	CO-Hb (%) in blood	Physiological symptoms
0.007	10	No appreciable effects except shortness of breath on vigorous exertion
0.035-0.052	40-50	Headache, confusion, collapse in exertion
0.080-0.122	60-70	Unconsciousness, intermittent, convulsion
0.122-0.195	70-80	Rapid death

During fire and explosion the time to remain trapped in underground is uncertain and the mental condition of mineworker may become quite volatile during this period. Such as Sago mine explosion in USA, on 2nd January 2006 thirteen miners were trapped and had to fight for continued survival in underground coal mine. Ultimately twelve miners lost their lives after forty hours of continued existence. The sole survival Jr. Mac Cloy who won life after fighting with disaster. He mentioned that they were having thirteen chemical type Self Contained Self Rescuers (SCSR), out of which four were not working. At the place of casualties in the Sago mine the concentration of CO was 300 ppm to 400 ppm (0.03% to 0.04%) in the mine air⁵.

Filter type self rescuer (FSR) is an escape type life saving safety breathing apparatus, which does not produce oxygen but it converts carbon monoxide to non-poisonous carbon dioxide. FSR provides safety to underground coal mining workers against possibility of respiratory failure due to sudden exposure to CO gas in the

breathing atmosphere. The cartridge of FSR has two beds separated by fine wire net. The lower portion is filled with activated charcoal while upper portion is filled with copper manganese oxide hopcalite CuMn₂O₄^{6,7}. Atmospheric oxygen (O₂) breaks in 2O which is readily available for oxidation of two molecule of CO in presence of hopcalite as per the following reaction.

Parameters evaluated for quality assurance of FSR :

Bureau of Indian Standard formulated a method (BIS : 9563-1980) for performance evaluation of FSR to insure its quality. The performance evaluation of FSR are evaluated by open circuit artificial mechanical human lung simulation machine.

CIMFR, Dhanbad is one of the Institute in India accredited for carrying out the quality evaluation of FSR by using 99.9% pure CO gas. The given laboratory tests are essential for FSR before its use in underground coal mine fire and disaster. The parameters for major laboratory tests with their prescribed limits are given as below⁸.

Sl. no.	Type of test	Prescribed limit
1.	Easy opening test	FSR should open without using any tools
2.	Weight gain test	FSR should not gain weight more than 5.0 g
3.	Deformation test	FSR should not generate bad smell during heating inside of air oven at 150 °C for 5 min
4.	Rattling test	FSR subject to impact of 50000 in 10 h and there should not be residue at the bottom of canister
5.	Water vapour tightness test	FSR should not gain weight during 80 °C heating and cooling at R.T. for 5 days
6.	CO conversion test	FSR should not liberate more than 100 ppm during penetration test at 2500, 5000 and 10000 ppm of CO, each test carry three no. of FSRs for one hour
7.	Temperature test	Inhalation temperature of FSR should not exceed 65 °C at 15000 ppm of CO penetration test for an hour
8.	Breathing resistance test	FSR should not have breathing inhalation resistance 65.0 mm wg and 80.0 mm wg before and after CO penetration test. Similarly exhalation resistance should not more than 20.0 mm wg

Rectification of limitation and drawback in FSR :

As per the present need of production of coal, the possibility of deeper expansion of underground coal mining may not be ruled out. Under such circumstances the use of an escape safety breathing apparatus will be required for longer duration. Chemical oxygen type self rescuer provides pure oxygen to the trapped persons during emergency till Super Oxide (KO₂) is available in the cartridge for specific duration⁹.

Filter typed self rescuer is based on catalytic reaction and it can work in polluted atmosphere for more than specified period during emergency, if atleast 17% of oxygen is present in the atmosphere. Hopcalite convert CO into CO₂ while the dryness of hopcalite is maintained by activated charcoal. The limitation and drawback of filter type self rescuers are needed for its rectification of longer duration. The drawback of canister of FSR is the rise in

the canister can be reduced by the attachment of a neoprene corrugated breathing pipe inside with spiral metal wire of suitable heat exchanger. The distance between teeth bite of mouth piece and canister may be twelve to fifteen inches to reduce the inhalation temperature. The additional attachment of supportive filter (Fig. 2) at the bottom of canister will protect from choking due to polluted underground mine air after fire and explosion. From the experiences of carrying out quality-control evaluation of FSRs from different manufacturers such as MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata, Joseph Leslie Dragger (Germany), Fraser (Poland) and AZL-60 Hunan Coal Company (China), it was observed that the breathing resistance of filter type self rescuer of MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata is suitable for replaceable air filter. The comparative breathing resistance of FSR canister with reference to Indian Standard is given as below in the Table.

Parameters	IS : 9563-1980		MSA (I) Ltd.,		Hunan Coal		Fraser of	
	Clause No. 4.1		India		Company, China		Poland	
	Int.	Fin.	Int.	Fin.	Int.	Fin.	Int.	Fin.
Inhalation breathing resistance	65	80	35	45	45	55	60	70
	(mm of H ₂ O)		(mm of H ₂ O)		(mm of H ₂ O)		(mm of H ₂ O)	

temperature of inhalation air creates swelling in mouth and breathing discomfort of underground mineworkers. After fire and explosion the coal fine particles, carbon soot and dust are major pollutants in the breathing air of underground coal mines. The second major drawback of FSR is its failure to filter these pollutants and choking creates rise in breathing resistance within the canister of users. One of the filter type self rescuer made by MSA (India) Ltd., was evaluated for specific CO conversion test in open circuit artificial mechanical human lung simulation machine. The test was carried out at 20000 ppm of 99.99% pure carbon monoxide gas. After 8 h of CO penetration test in 95 to 98% humidity chamber the catalyst of cartridge of FSR was observed active. The inhalation temperature at mouth piece raised up to 62 °C¹⁰. After this observation it is found if generated heat due to conversion of CO into CO₂ in the canister is dissipated then FSR can be used more than the prescribed limitation of time in emergency. The effect of generated heat within

Fig. 1. Breathing tube attachment with mouthpiece of FSR.

Fig. 2. Image of replaceable filter.

Fig. 3. Cartridge of FSR.

As per above table of Indian Standard IS : 9563-1980 clause no. 4.1, an additional breathing resistance up to 25.0 mm wg of air filter can be attached at the bottom of FSR made by MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata as given in the Fig. 2.

The image of breathing tube attachment in Fig. 1, replaceable air filter in Fig. 2 and diagram of cartridge of FSR in Fig. 3 are given.

Conclusion

After fire and explosion in underground coal mines workers have to trapped below underground for several hours. The modified design of laboratory approved filter

typed self rescuer of MSA (India) Ltd., Kolkata can support mine workers for several hours breath in the underground coal mines. The improved FSR may be life saving escape safety breathing apparatus at cost effective price for the smoky fire in high rise building of metro cites. The necessary initiative for improvement in the design of filter type self rescuer taken by Ministry of Coal, Ministry of Steel & Mines and Ministry of Urban Development will help to save the human life and may provide a better safety breathing apparatus to underground mine workers and rescuers of high rise building.

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